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Research Article

**STABILITY INDICATING HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID
CHROMATOGRAPHY FOR THE DETERMINATION OF
LINAGLIPTIN IN BULK AND TABLET DOSAGE FORM.**Y.Neelima¹ and Y.Kranthi Kumar^{2*}¹Research Scholar, Prathibha Degree and PG College, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.²Research Scholar, RGR Siddhanthi College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.**Abstract:**

The Reverse Phase High Performance Liquid Chromatographic method was developed for the determination of linagliptin with its stability studies in its bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form which was precise, accurate and sensitive. The separation has been done by using the chromatographic conditions on an Inertsil ODS column (250 x 4.6 mm, 5 μ particle size), the mobile phase of potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer pH 6 and acetonitrile in the ratio 60:40 v/v, at a flow rate of 1 mL/min at an ambient temperature at a wavelength 246 nm at retention time of 3.67 minutes. The method developed was validated for specificity, precision, linearity, accuracy and forced degradation stability studies. The average recoveries of linagliptin were 98.0 – 102.0% and thereof a good linear relationship ($r^2=0.999$) was observed between the concentration range of linearity in the range of 25-150% with respect to test concentration (12.5-75.0 μ g/mL) and the above proposed method was validated for various parameters as per ICH guidelines and all the results obtained were satisfactory and passed all the forced degradation stability studies.

Keywords: *Forced Degradation Stability studies, Linagliptin, Separation.***Corresponding author:****Y.Kranthi Kumar,**

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1. INTRODUCTION:

Linagliptin is a DPP-4 inhibitor developed by Boehringer Ingelheim for treatment of type II diabetes. It is an inhibitor of DPP-4¹⁻², an enzyme that degrades the incretin hormones glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) and glucose-dependent insulinotropic polypeptide (GIP). Linagliptin chemically known as 8-[(3*R*)-3-aminopiperidin-1-yl]-7-(but-2-yn-1-yl)-3-methyl-1-[(4-methylquinazolin-2-yl)methyl]-3,7-dihydro-1*H*-purine-2,6-dione (Fig 1).

Fig 1: Structure of Linagliptin

The literature survey ensures that the developed analytical methods which include the UV spectrophotometric methods³⁻⁴, some liquid chromatographic methods⁵⁻⁹, simultaneous UV spectrophotometric methods with hplc¹⁰ and simultaneous determination of two drugs by using hplc¹¹⁻¹². The above proposed method developed is the stability indicating studies - high performance liquid chromatography method for determination of linagliptin in presence of its degradation products for assurance of the purity of the bulk drug and stability of pharmaceutical dosage form which is validated, accurate, precise and sensitive.

2. EXPERIMENTAL:

2.1 Materials

Linagliptin was supplied as a gift sample from Emcure pharmaceuticals Ltd. All HPLC grade methanol, acetonitrile and orthophosphoric acids and potassium di hydrogen phosphate were obtained from S.D. Fine Chemicals Ltd., India, Qualigens Fine Chemicals Ltd., Mumbai, India.

2.2 Instrumentation

A HPLC used with the chromatographic system made of Waters consists of binary pump, auto sampler with PDA detector. Data acquisition was done by using empower 2 software. The column used was C₁₈, (250 X 4.6 mm, 5μ) with mobile phase KH₂PO₄ buffer: ACN (60: 40) v/v at a flow rate of 1 ml/min at a wavelength of 246 nm.

2.3 Preparation of solutions

2.3.1 Preparation of buffer

A 0.01 M solution of potassium dihydrogen phosphate was prepared by dissolving 0.680 g of

potassium dihydrogen phosphate in 800 ml water and diluting to 1000 ml with water.

2.3.2 Preparation of stock solution

Weigh and transfer 5 mg of Linagliptin working standard into 10 mL volumetric flask, add 5 mL of diluent and sonicate to dissolve and dilute the remaining volume with diluent.

2.3.3 Preparation of sample solution

Finely grind pre weighed 20 tablets. Transfer grinded sample quantitatively equivalent to 5 mg of Linagliptin in to 10 mL volumetric flask add 5 mL of diluent, sonicate to dissolve for 10 minutes and dilute to volume with diluent. Further filter the solution through filter paper. Dilute 1 mL of filtrate to 10 mL with mobile phase.

2.4 Method Validation

The developed method will be validated by the determination of the parameters like system suitability, linearity, accuracy and precision, specificity, ruggedness and robustness as per ICH guidelines.

2.5 Forced Degradation Studies

To perform the forced degradation study 10 mL of the tablet sample solution (50 μg/mL concentration) drug was subjected to acidic, alkaline, thermal and UV radiation conditions. For acidic degradation the drug was taken to it 10 mL of 0.1N HCl was added and was exposed to heat at a temperature of 60⁰ C for 30 mins. For alkaline degradation the drug was treated with 10 mL of 1N NaOH and was exposed to heat at a temperature of 60⁰ C for 30 mins. For thermal degradation the powdered drug was exposed to heat at a temperature of 100⁰ C in oven drier exposure for about 5 hours. For UV degradation, powdered drug was exposed to UV chamber for about 12 hrs and later the above solutions were made up to 100 mL using water.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

3.1 Method Development

The method is developed by using the suitable chromatographic system conditions by using the mobile phase KH₂PO₄ buffer: ACN (60: 40) v/v at a flow rate of 1 ml/min at a wavelength of 246 nm by using the column C₁₈. The standard chromatogram (Fig 2) is developed by using the standard stock solution and further the validation and their parameters are achieved as per ICH guidelines.

Fig 2. Standard chromatogram of Linagliptin

3.1.1 System Suitability Studies

For system suitability, six replicate injections of the working standard or sample solution were injected and the system suitability parameters were evaluated. The results of system suitability were shown in **Table 1**.

Table 1: System Suitability Studies of Linagliptin

S.No.	Retention Time (min)	Peak Area	Plate Count (N)	Tailing factor
1	3.62	3147697	5670	1.15
2	3.615	3178410	5703	1.13
3	3.614	3171498	5730	1.14
4	3.616	3161334	5703	1.14
5	3.615	3172960	5713	1.13
6	3.618	3207718	5484	1.15
Avg	3.6163	3173269.5		
Std.dev	0.002250926	20063.73251		
%RSD	0.06	0.63		

3.1.2 Specificity

The specificity of the developed method was determined by injecting blank, placebo solution, individual standards, mixed standard and sample solution separately.

3.1.3 Linearity

The linearity study was performed for the concentration range of 12.5-75 µg/mL for Linagliptin. Each level was injected into chromatographic system and calibration curve was plotted and the graph shown at **Fig 3**.

Fig 3: Linearity of Linagliptin

3.1.4 Accuracy

The accuracy of the developed method was evaluated by injecting triplicates of solutions of concentration 50%, 100% and 150%. The individual recovery and mean recovery values were calculated from the amount added and amount found the results obtained are shown in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Results of Accuracy of Linagliptin

Category	Standard	50% Solution	100 % Solution	150% Solution
Inj1 (Peak Area)	3152468	1568452	3186541	4765851
Inj2 (Peak Area)	3186542	1578655	3152486	4658725
Inj3 (Peak Area)	3175584	1572140	3155524	4721543
AVG	3171531	1573082	3164850	4715373
Std.dev	17394.75	5166.362	18845.98	53828.86
%RSD	0.548465	0.328423	0.595478	1.141561
Amount Recovered		49.60	99.79	148.68
%Recovery		99.20	99.79	99.12

3.1.5 Precision

The precision of the method was ascertained separately from the peak area obtained by actual determination of six replicas of a fixed amount of the drug and formulation. The precision of this method was checked by repeatability of injection, repeatability (intra-assay), intermediate precision (inter assay) and reproducibility. Injection repeatability was studied by calculating the

percentage relative standard deviation (%RSD) for ten determinations of peak areas of Linagliptin performed on the same day for both intra- and inter-assay variation, standard solutions of linagliptin.

3.1.6 LOD and LOQ

The LOD and LOQ of linagliptin was estimated from signal to noise ratio and were found to be 1.5 µg/mL and 4 µg/mL respectively and the chromatograms were shown at **Fig 4 & 5**.

Fig 4: Chromatogram of LOD

Fig 5: Chromatogram of LOQ

3.1.6 Robustness

Robustness of the method was determined by changing experimental conditions deliberately. The effect of change in flow rate and wavelength on retention time, theoretical plate number and peak asymmetry were studied and the results were shown in **Table 3**.

Table 3: Results of Robustness

Condition	Theoretical Plates (NLT 2500)	Symmetry Factor (NMT2.0)
Buffer-1	5915	1.13
Buffer-2	5959	1.13
Flow rate 1 mL	5140	1.13
Flow rate 1.2mL	6421	1.15

3.2 Forced Degradation Studies

3.2.1 Acid Degradation

10 mL of the sample solution (50 µg/mL concentration) was taken and to it 10 mL of 1N HCl was added and was exposed to heat at a temperature of 60° C for 30 min. Later this solution was made up to 100 mL using water. This solution was then chromatographed and the results were shown in **Fig 6**.

Fig 6: Chromatogram of Acid Degradation.

3.2.2 Alkali Degradation

10 mL of the sample solution (50 µg/mL concentration) was taken and to it 10 mL of 1N NaOH was added and was exposed to heat at a temperature of 60° C for 30 min. Later this solution was made up to 100 mL using water. This solution was then chromatographed and the results were shown in **Fig 7**.

Fig 7: Chromatogram of Alkali Degradation

Table 4: Results of Stability Studies

S.No	Parameter	RT (min)	Peak Area	%Purity	%Impurity
1	Degradation in acid	3.555	3072244	98.55	1.38
2	Degradation in base	3.627	2301510	99.07	0.93
3	Degradation on heat	3.555	3075654	98.55	1.45
4	Degradation to light	3.627	2300878	98.74	0.95

3.2.3 Thermal Degradation

The thermal degraded sample has the R_t Value of 3.55 and degradation was not observed in standard that was exposed to temperature of 105° C for 30 min.

3.5.4. UV radiation degradation

The samples was not degraded under uv radiation for about 2 hrs and the dry heat conditions and showed peak at R-value of 3.66.

This indicates that the drug is susceptible to acid / base hydrolysis, uv radiation and thermal degradation.

The results of accelerated degradation studies are listed in **Table 4**.

There are many spectrophotometric and liquid chromatographic methods for determination of Linagliptin but the present study of stability indicating high performance liquid chromatography for the determination of linagliptin in its bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form is linear, accurate, precise, rapid, selective, reproducible and sensitive for the estimation of the drug in quality control department in the pharmaceutical industry.

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